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Research Article

Prospective Open Label Study To Evaluate The Safety And Efficacy Of Diabenol: A Homeopathic Remedy For Diabetes Mellitus

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ABSTRACT

Objective: This study was conducted to evaluate the efficacy of homeopathic medicine “diabenol” in diabetes mellitus patients

Method: This was the six month prospective open label study. Total 73 patients were enrolled according to our set inclusion criteria and diabenol was given them 2 teaspoon thrice a day. Their HbA1c and blood sugar levels were monitored regularly. All the patients were advised to visit as per set schedule.

Result: All patients were categorized according to their gender, age, BMI and medicines taken previously. Out of 73 patients only 37 patients completed their treatment till six months and all patients showed statistically significant result in their blood sugar and HbA1c levels in all study groups. Diabenol also played an important role to enhance the quality of life among diabetic patients and also equally beneficial in reducing symptoms like frequent urination, disturbance in sleep, lethargy, numbness and muscle pain.

Conclusion: Homeopathic medicine “diabenol” is effective in diabetes mellitus patients. Patient should be encouraged to take homeopathic drugs as an alternative and complementary medicine especially for chronic conditions like diabetes

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INTRODUCTION:

Diabetes mellitus is a hyperglycemic metabolic syndrome which occurs due to defect in insulin action, its secretion, or both.(1) Basically it disturbs the metabolism of fats, carbohydrates and protein.(2, 3) The persistent rise in blood glucose levels is associated with long term damage, disturbance in functioning and failure of many organs particularly kidney, heart, nerves, eyes and blood vessels.(1, 3, 4) Diabetes is a leading cause of morbidity and mortality.(5-7). In recent years, associated factors in increasing diabetes prevalence are sedentary lifestyle, obesity, ageing, unhealthy diet and urbanization.(6, 8, 9) Patients with type 2 diabetes are at greater risk for various health problems like cardiovascular disease, nephropathy, retinopathy, premature death and amputation.(10) Furthermore, higher rate of hospitalization, blindness, renal failure and non-traumatic amputation are also associated with diabetes.(6)

According to World Health Organization (WHO), there are about 143 million sufferers worldwide and this number is expected to rise almost 300 million by 2025. Most diabetic patients have type 2 diabetes and almost all are at risk of developing complications.(11-13) Globally, diabetes mellitus is a growing health problem and the prevalence of diabetes is increasing.(14, 15) In Pakistan, prevalence of diabetes in adult population is more than 10%.(16, 17) Diabetes is the fourth leading cause of death in developed countries and Pakistan ranked at seventh position. Both type 1 and type 2 diabetes mellitus rapidly spreading worldwide but type 2 diabetes prevalence is rising more rapidly.(18)

Recent era offers not only allopathic medicines as a form of western medical treatment but also many alternative forms of treatment like homeopathy. In acute and chronic conditions of disease, homeopathy found to be very effective. However in Pakistan, there is a lack of sufficient evidence regarding the homeopathic remedies.(19) Thus main goal of our current clinical trial aimed to evaluate the efficacy of homeopathic medicine "Diabenol" for the treatment of type 2 diabetes,

STUDY DESIGN AND METHODS

This prospective observational study was carried out to evaluate the safety and efficacy of Diabenol. Diabenol is basically a combination of two ingredients amygdalus and murraya. Flower part of amygdalus and leaf, root and bark part of murraya are used for the

preparation of Diabenol. The study was conducted in Pakistan homeopathic research center and for this purpose ethics approval was sought and granted by institutional committee of clinical research. The study duration was 6 Months.

INCLUSION CRITERIA:

Both male and female patients of age 30-60 years with type 2 diabetes and whose body mass index not was more than 25 to 35 kg/m² were included in the study. Patients whose Fasting sugar >126 mg/dl, Postprandial glucose level >200mg/dl and HbA1c >6.5 were included. Subject willing and able to provide written informed consent and showed interest for future visits were also included

EXCLUSION CRITERIA

Patient above 75 years and with other type of diabetes were excluded. Insulin dependent and hospitalized patients were not included in the study. Patients with the history or presence of clinically serious disease including triple vessel, respiratory, liver cirrhosis, renal failure, gastrointestinal, gangrene and diabetic retinopathy, cognitive and psychotic disorders were not enrolled. Patients who showed no interest for future visit to study sites and or participant physicians were also excluded. Pregnant and lactating mothers were not enrolled

DATA COLLECTION

All patients visited homeopathic clinic were assessed for eligibility. Patients inducted according to the pre-defined inclusion criteria. The informed consent was taken from the patients and those who showed no interest for future visit to study sites were excluded. A short history was taken from all selected patients. Then we checked their blood sugar levels and recorded them in data collection form. Blood samples were taken and send to concerned laboratory for analysis. Patients were advised to visit next day. Next day we received all blood reports and once they fulfilled our inclusion criteria then the patients were enrolled. Information regarding patient's demographics was taken. Physical assessments of all patients were done by qualified doctor and laboratory findings were recorded on data collection form. Qualified pharmacist counseled them regarding their diet planes, and also motivated them to adopt a healthy lifestyle. A counseling session usually lasted for 15-20 minutes. Standard dose of diabenol was prescribed to all patients. The patients were advised to come for checkup as per scheduled visits

(Figure 1). The patients were contacted through telephonic calls or short message service. We enrolled total 73 patients for this study. On every follow-up all

the direct and indirect parameters were assessed and recorded carefully. Patients sample for HbA_{1c} were also taken after every three months.

Figure 1: Over view of study

RESULTS

Total 73 patients were enrolled with type 2 diabetes according to our inclusion and exclusion criteria. Baseline information of all patients was given in table 1 and 2. Only 37 patients were able to complete the follow up of six month and 36 patients drop from the study due to certain reasons. All the basic parameters were recorded at baseline including their demographic, family history, diabetes complications

and physical activity, smoking history, medicines, and dietary details. Blood pressure trend of diabetic patients was recorded on every visit mentioned in table no 2. At baseline, average systolic blood pressure was 129.86±20.08 which was decreased to 127.29±18.98 at the end of six months and average diastolic blood pressure at baseline was 84.18±11.51 which was decreased to 84.59±10.43 at the end of six months.

Table 1: Demographics

Parameters	Follow-up of three month	Complete follow-up for six months	Total
Gender			
Male	25 (69.4)	25(67.6)	50(68.5)
Female	11(30.6)	12(32.4)	23(31.5)

Family history			
No	1(2.8)	9(24.3)	10(13.7)
Yes	35(97.2)	28(75.7)	63(86.3)
Smoking			
Yes	32(88.9)	36(97.3)	68(93.2)
Occasionally	1(2.8)	0(0.0)	1(1.4)
No	3(8.3)	1(2.7)	4(5.5)
Total	36(100)	37(100)	73(100)
Marital status			
Widow	4(11.1)	2(5.4)	6(8.2)
Married	31(86.1)	35(94.6)	66(90.4)
Unmarried	1(2.8)	0(0.0)	1(1.4)
Total	36(100.0)	37(100.0)	73(100.0)
Diabetes related complication			
Heart complications			
Yes	34(94.4)	30(81.1)	64(87.7)
No	2(5.6)	7(18.9)	9(12.3)
Kidney			
Yes	34(94.4)	37(100.0)	71(97.3)
No	2(5.6)	0(0.0)	2(2.7)
Retinopathy			
Yes	32(88.9)	33(89.2)	65(89.0)
No	4(11.1)	4(10.0)	8(11.0)
Neuropathy			
Yes	20(55.6)	22(59.5)	42(57.5)
No	16(44.6)	15(40.5)	31(42.5)
Any infections			
Yes	0(0.0)	0(0.0)	0(0.0)
No	36(100.0)	37(100.0)	73(100.0)
Hypertension			
Yes	34(94.4)	31(83.8)	65(89.0)
No	2(2.6)	6(16.2)	8(11.0)
Total	36(100.0)	37(100.0)	73(100.0)
Erectile dysfunction			
Yes	0(0.0)	0(0.0)	0(0.0)
No	36(100.0)	37(100.0)	73(100.0)
Total	36(100.0)	37(100.0)	73(100.0)
Intermittent claudication			
Yes	0(0.0)	0(0.0)	0(0.0)
No	36(100.0)	37(100.0)	73(100.0)
Total	36(100.0)	37(100.0)	73(100.0)
Cerebrovascular disease			
Yes	0(0.0)	0(0.0)	0(0.0)
No	36(100.0)	37(100.0)	73(100.0)
Total	36(100.0)	37(100.0)	73(100.0)
Abnormal ECG			
YES	36(100.0)	36(97.3)	72(98.6)
NO	0(0.0)	1(2.7)	1(1.4)
Total	36(100.0)	37(100.0)	73(100.0)
Weight loss program			
Yes	0(0.0)	0(0.0)	0(0.0)
No	36(100.0)	37(100.0)	73(100.0)
Total	36(100.0)	37(100.0)	73(100.0)

Physical activity			
More than 30 min	6(16.7)	7(18.9)	13(17.9)
Less than 30 min	18(50.0)	15(40.8)	33(45.2)
No walk	12(33.3)	15(40.5)	27(37.0)
Total	36(100.0)	37(100.0)	73(100.0)

Table 2: Blood pressure trend

Parameters	Mean ± S.D
Systolic blood pressure-Baseline	129.86±20.08
Systolic blood pressure- 1 st Follow up	127.43±21.46
Systolic blood pressure- 2 nd Follow up	123.24±16.33
Systolic blood pressure- 3 rd Follow up	124.73±14.71
Systolic blood pressure- 4 th Follow up	125.94±12.12
Systolic blood pressure-5 th Follow up	127.29±18.98
Diastolic blood pressure- Baseline	84.18±11.51
Diastolic blood pressure-1 st Follow up	83.78±12.04
Diastolic blood pressure - 2 nd Follow up	83.24±10.01
Diastolic blood pressure- 3 rd Follow up	80.89±8.5
Diastolic blood pressure-4 th Follow up	85.81±8.29
Diastolic blood pressure- 5 th Follow up	84.59±10.43

Table 3: Change in HbA1c level in study population

Parameters	HbA1c Baseline	HbA1c After three months	HbA1c After six month
Total patients			
Total	9.38±2.13	8.59±1.75	7.44±1.45
% Reduction	Ref	8.42	20.68
p-value	Ref	.008*	.000***
Gender			
Male			
	9.35±1.93	8.69±1.68	7.56±1.61
% Reduction	Ref	7.05	19.1
p-value	Ref	.036*	.000***
Female			
	9.45±2.59	8.40±1.94	7.18±1.05
% Reduction	Ref	11.11	24.02
p-value	Ref	.113	.013*
Age			
<50 years			
	9.914±2.007	8.71±1.619	7.79±1.569
% Reduction	Ref	12.1	21.3
p-value	Ref	.006*	.000***
>50 years			
	8.66±2.14	8.44±1.952	6.97±1.16
% Reduction	Ref	2.54	19.5
p-value	Ref	.522	.006*
Normal weight			
	9.73±2.37	9.02±1.866	7.71±1.69
% Reduction	Ref	7.29	20.7
p-value	Ref	.189	.016*
Over weight patients			
	9.03±1.67	8.10±1.39	7.16±1.22
% Reduction	Ref	10.29	20.7
p-value	Ref	.073	.004**

Obese patient	9.50±2.65	8.90±2.11	7.57±1.554
% Reduction	Ref	6.31	20.3
p-value	Ref	.145	.019*
Homeopathic medicines	9.78±1.94	8.70±1.776	7.92±1.83
% Reduction	Ref	11.04	19.0
p-value	Ref	.011*	.003**
Allopathic medicines	9.15±2.26	8.54±1.77	7.17±1.146
% Reduction	Ref	6.66	21.6
p-value	Ref	.118	.001**

Table 4: Change in blood sugar fasting level in study population

Parameters	BSF-B	BSF-1	BSF-2	BSF-3	BSF-4	BSF-5
Total patients						
Total	191.49±64.82	189.29±63.58	178.75±60.55	159.189±44.08	149.351±34.26	130.81±27.34
% Reduction	Ref	1.14	6.64	16.86	22.00	31.68
P value	Ref	.79	.223	.001***	.000***	.000***
Gender						
Female	206.500±83.29	211.500±84.851	166.583±44.795	167.33±46.338	158.583±33.268	134.250±28.56
% Reduction	Ref	-2.421	19.33	18.96	23.20	34.98
P value	Ref	.696	.027*	.100	.049*	.003**
Male	184.280±54.37	178.640±48.98	184.600±66.86	155.280±43.38	144.920±34.518	129.160±27.18
% Reduction	Ref	3.060	-0.17	15.73	21.35	29.21
P value	Ref	.610	.980	.002**	.002**	.000***
Age						
< 50 years	201.57±66.79	191.71±62.21	175.90±53.70	161.19±42.78	153.14±38.27	130.23±27.34
% Reduction	Ref	4.891	12.73	20.03	24.02	35.39
P value	Ref	.265	.034*	.005**	.004**	.000***
> 50 years	178.25±61.70	186.12±67.25	182.50±70.20	156.76±47.01	144.37±28.60	131.56±28.22
% Reduction	Ref	-4.41	-3.50	12.05	19.00	26.19
P value	Ref	.622	.818	.083	.24	.003**
BMI						
Normal weight	178.08±44.97	196.50±52.46	168.00±43.06	171.16±46.71	144.91±30.61	126.25±18.72
% Reduction	Ref	-10.34	5.66	3.88	18.62	29.10
P value	Ref	.280	.476	.533	.28	.002**
Over weight	180.31±52.61	173.500±70.12	177.56±68.82	143.31±29.03	148.62±37.27	127.12±26.12
% Reduction	Ref	3.77	1.52	20.52	17.57	29.49
P value	Ref	.575	.893	.32	.071	.002**
Obese patient	229.22±93.89	207.77±65.00	195.22±67.73	171.44±57.24	156.55±36.06	143.44±36.94
% Reduction	Ref	9.35	14.83	25.20	31.70	37.42
P value	Ref	.181	.041*	.006*	.016*	.008*
Allopathic medicine	188.20±67.19	192.00±66.74	176.33±67.36	164.54±46.50	153.75±34.32	129.83±26.30
% Reduction	Ref	-2.01	6.30	12.57	18.30	31.01

P value	Ref	.682	.442	.059	.025*	.000***
Homeopathic medicine	197.53±62.38	184.30±59.56	183.23±47.62	149.30±39.02	141.23±33.99	132.61±30.20
% Reduction	Ref	6.69	7.23	24.41	28.50	32.86
P value	Ref	.447	.148	.002**	.000***	.000***

Table 5: Change in blood sugar random level in study population

Parameters	BSR-B	BSR-1	BSR-2	BSR-3	BSR-4	BSR-5
Total	308.45± 100.39	269.37± 84.44	228.59± 81.09	221.32 ±74.93	196.43± 52.85	181.45 ±55.17
% Reduction	Ref	12.66	25.89	28.24	36.31	41.17
P value	Ref	.001***	.000***	.000***	.000***	.000***
Gender						
Male	308.04± 102.91	276.76 ±75.44	229.16± 80.81	216.68± 77.65	196.52 ±55.85	183.96± 55.73
% Reduction	Ref	10.15	25.60	29.65	36.20	40.28
P value	Ref	.035*	.001***	.000***	.000***	.000***
Total female	309.33 ±99.39	254.00 ±102.66	227.41 ±85.27	231.00± 71.17	196.25± 48.33	176.25 ±56.04
% Reduction	Ref	17.88	26.48	25.32	36.55	43.02
P value	Ref	.007*	.004**	.026*	.002**	.000***
Age						
< 50 years	323.81±112.38	268.19±82.48	220.85±79.36	216.66±73.53	191.33±51.22	177.85±53.99
% Reduction	Ref	17.17	31.79	33.09	40.91	45.07
P value	Ref	.001***	.000***	.000*	.000***	.000***
> 50 years	288.31 ±81.16	270.93± 89.65	238.75± 84.79	227.43 ±78.70	203.12± 55.87	186.18± 58.10
% Reduction	Ref	6.02	17.18	21.11	29.54	35.42
P value	Ref	.297	.060	.015*	.001***	.000***
GENDER						
Normal weight	308.91±100.84	286.00±79.91	230.08±85.23	256.25±78.57	207.91±67.11	180.91±55.49
% Reduction	Ref	7.41	25.51	17.04	32.69	41.43
P value	Ref	.317	.032	.066	.002**	.000***
Over weight	288.75±85.71	261.25±87.17	220.188±65.06	186.56±47.93	192.75±49.12	165.50±46.75
% Reduction	Ref	9.52	23.74	35.39	33.24	42.68
P value	Ref	.062	.013*	.001***	.001***	.000***
Obese patient	342.88±124.45	261.66±91.90	241.55±106.45	236.55±89.22	187.66±39.25	210.55±62.47
% Reduction	Ref	23.68	29.55	31.01	45.26	38.59
P value	Ref	.005**	.011*	.007*	.003**	.001***
Allopathic	280.45±83.60	261.45±94.73	229.25±76.94	215.50±64.12	190.37±50.49	165.25±47.56
% Reduction	Ref	6.77	18.25	23.15	32.11	41.07
P value	Ref	.129	.008*	.003***	.000***	.000***
Homeopathic	360.15±111.25	284.00±61.94	227.38±91.53	232.07±93.64	207.61±57.32	211.38±57.44
% Reduction	Ref	21.14	36.86	35.56	42.35	41.30
P value	Ref	.001***	.001***	.000**	.000***	.000***

BSF-B, Blood sugar fasting at baseline; BSR-B Blood sugar random at baseline; p-value= <0.05* significant, 0.005** very significant, <0.001*** highly significant; HbA1c, glycated hemoglobin

Figure 2: main symptoms

2B

2C

HbA_{1c} levels of all 37 patients who completed six months follow up were analyzed as shown in table 3. Overall reduction in their glycated hemoglobin (HbA_{1c}) levels was seen which was highly significant. Both female and male group showed significant reduction but female HbA_{1c} levels (24.02%) showed more percentage reduction than male (19.1%). Between age groups, patients with age <50 years showed more reduction (21.3%) and then the patients with >50 years of age (19.5%). At baseline, their average hba1c value was 9.914±2.00 among the age group of <50 years and after six months their average hba1c values were 7.79 ±1.56. It means that, after use of homeopathic medicines Diabenol, this age group showed better response. We also categorized the patients according to their body mass index. We categorized them in three group (normal weight, overweight and obese patients) and analyzed their hba1c response. In all three groups, equally significant reduction was seen in their HbA_{1c} values (20.7%). According to their therapeutic interventions two group were made, one allopathic and second was homeopathic. In allopathic group we incorporated those patients who were previously using oral hypoglycemic medicine and in homeopathic group we incorporated those patients who were previously using no medicines or already taking homeopathic medicine (Diabenol). Patients who were using allopathic medicine group showed more significant reduction in their average hba1c values (9.15±2.26) when compared to baseline value HbA_{1c} values (7.17±1.14).

In Table 4, the blood sugar fasting (BSF) levels of 37 patients were analyzed and overall significant reduction was seen in their values. At baseline their BSF value was 191.49± 64.82 and on completion of six month their blood sugar fasting value was 130.81 ±27.34. Overall 31.68 % reduction was seen at the end of six month which was a significant reduction from baseline value. Both male (n=25) and female group(n=12) showed very good result in their BSF values but female group showed more significant (34.98% reduction) trend than male group (29.21). Young patients with age <50 years showed more reduction in BSF levels than the patients with above 50 years of age. Total 35.34 % reduction was seen in patients with age group <50 years. While in patients with above 50 years of age total 26.19 % reduction was observed. 12 patients were in normal weight category, 6 patients were in over- weight group and 16 patients in obese group. Obese patients showed good reduction in their BSF levels 37.42% whereas 29.10% reduction was seen in normal weight group and 29.49% reduction in over- weight group. Thirteen patients were on homeopathic medicine at baseline and twenty four were on allopathic medicine. In homeopathic medicine group

(32.86% reduction) more reduction was seen than allopathic medicine (31.01% reduction).

Blood sugar random (BSR) of 37 patients was taken and analyzed in table 4. First their blood sugar random was checked at baseline. Then on every visit their BSR was also recorded. Average blood sugar random at baseline was 308.45± 100.39 which was significantly reduced to 181.45 ±55.17 till six months and overall 41.17 % reduction was seen in BSR of 37 patients. When we analyzed BSR according to gender it was noted a significant reduction was seen in both male and female group. Total 40.28% reduction in male group and 43.02% reduction was noted in female group. While in less than 50 years age group 45.07% and above 50 years of age group 35.42% reduction was seen. In normal weight group, 308.91±100.84 blood sugar random was noted at baseline and it was reduced to 180.91±55.49 till six months and overall 41.43% reduction was observed. Among over- weight group % reduction was 42.68 and in obese patients 38.59 % reduction. Overall 41.07 % reduction was seen in allopathic group and 41.30% reduction was in homeopathic group.

Frequent urination, numbness, disturbance in sleeping pattern, muscle pain and lethargy are the five major complaints among diabetic patients. Almost every patient came with these symptoms. After taking diabenol all patients showed reduction in the severity of these symptoms as shown in figure A. All these signs measures in 1 to 10 scale which read as (1= worse, 5= moderate, 10= good) and as we can see improvement in all signs. Sleep and fatigue pattern was also observed in all patients and overall improvement was seen as mention in figure 1-B and 1-C. Sleep pattern was measured as 0 mean never doze, 1 mean slight chance of dozing, 2 mean moderate chance of dozing and 3 mean high chance of dozing. As graph line indicated, sleep scale is improved. Fatigue scale was also measured as 1 mean strongly disagree and 7 mean strongly agree. We accumulated all answers and concluded that fatigue was also improved among all patients.

DISCUSSION:

Diabetes mellitus (DM) is a hyperglycemic metabolic syndrome which plays a main role in microvascular and macrovascular complications (1, 20-22) Diabetes mellitus is a growing health problem nowadays, which causes mortality, morbidity and long term complications.(23, 24) Prevalence of type 2 diabetes is rapidly increasing in both developed and developing countries.(25) Especially in Asia, diabetes type 2 changing in its presentation where people are more prone to risk factors for type 2 diabetes.(26) There are very limited conventional treatment options for DM. Thus our study was aimed at evaluating the

efficacy of homeopathic medicine “diabenol” among the diabetes patients. Homeopathy is a type of complementary and alternative medicines (11, 27) and it is commonly used for diabetes mellitus and its complications.(11)

The results of this prospective clinical trial in patients with type II diabetes indicate that diabenol effectively lowered blood glucose levels and hba1c levels. HbA1C level is a most common measure of glycemic control in clinical trials and for management of diabetes. HbA1C widely used as indicator for the measurement of blood glucose among the patients of diabetes.(28, 29) It is mentioned in previous epidemiological investigations that >6.5 HbA1C is enough to for diagnosing diabetes (20) that’s why we used HbA1C as an indicator in our study. All patients were categorized in different groups according to their age, gender, pharmacological intervention. The major finding of our study was that, HbA1C and blood sugar levels significantly improved after six months. We found highly significant results among 37 patients in their HbA1C, fasting blood glucose and random blood glucose levels. When we analyzed data according to gender: female group showed highest percentage reduction in Hba1c (24.02%) fasting (34.98%) and random blood glucose levels (43.02%), than male patients (HbA1C; 19.1%, BSF; 29.21%, BSR; 40.28%). Taken together, diabenol effectively controlled HbA1C and blood glucose levels (fasting and random blood glucose level) in both groups. We found high percentage reduction in patients of below 50 years of age (HbA1C; 21.3%, BSF; 35.39% and BSR; 45.07%) and less percentage reduction (HbA1C; 19.5%, BSF; 26.19% and BSR; 35.42% was found in above 50 year of age patients. Thus younger group showed good control in their blood sugar and HbA1C level. This might be because of sedentary life style of elderly people.(30) Physical activity is very important tool in the management of diabetes. Exercise have benefits both in terms of improved quality of life and metabolic control.(31) On the other hand normal (20.7%), over-weight (20.7%) and obese patient (20.3%) showed good percentage of reduction in their HbA1C levels. 12 patients were in normal weight category, 6 patients were in over- weight group and 16 patients in obese group. In obese category very good improvement was seen in fasting glucose levels (37.42%) while less percentage reduction was seen in normal (29.10%) and over-weight (29.49%). Diabetes mellitus and obesity are associated because in diabetic patients weight gain may be due to insulin resistance. Insulin resistance is a condition in which body unable to use insulin effectively.(32) Basically weight gain and obesity are contributory factors in increasing the risks associated with diabetes,(33) thus weight maintenance is

very important. In homeopathic and allopathic medicines group very significant trend was seen. Although the aim of our study was not on weight reduction but we promoted healthy lifestyle concept among patients. For healthy lifestyle, diet and exercise are very important especially in diabetes case.(34) Because exercise has beneficial effect in preventing and treating diabetes(35), that’s why we gave a balanced diet plan to patients and motivated them for exercise.

Despite variation in patients’ characteristics, diabenol found to be efficacious in all groups. Diabenol also showed good glycemic control in those patients, who were using both remedies (homeopathic and allopathic medicines). In homeopathic (HbA1C; 21.6%, BSF; 32.86%, BSR; 41.3%) and allopathic (HbA1C; 19.1%, BSF; 31.1%, BSR; 41.0%) medicines group very good percentage reduction was seen. For good glycemic control, diabenol is very effective that’s why highest percentage reduction was seen in blood sugar fasting, blood sugar random, and HbA1C levels of 37 patients in all groups. This result also strengthen our claim that diabenol very effective in controlling blood glucose levels.

Frequent urination, numbness, disturbance in sleeping pattern, muscle pain and lethargy are the five major complaints among diabetic patients. Almost every patient came with these symptoms. After taking diabenol, severity of these symptoms were improve. It improve the quality of life of patients and also helping in reducing severity of 5 symptoms. On every visit, their fatigue and sleeping status were assessed and their responses were recorded and analyzed. In both women and men who are at high risk for all disease, by lifestyle modification we can prevent diabetes.(36) Major finding of our medicine “dibenol” was it effectively control blood sugar levels as well as reduce symptom severity and enhance the quality of life among diabetic patients.

Hence it was proved that diabenol effectively reduced blood glucose and HbA1C levels in diabetes mellitus type 2 patients. Early treatment, self-care and regular screening can only limit the complications of diabetes (37) and we incorporated these three elements in our study. We provided information to patients how self-care, regular screening and proper treatment would help them in delaying diabetes complications. In previous study it was mentioned that, with good management we can limit or delayed the diabetes complications.(32)

CONCLUSION

We concluded that homeopathic medicine diabenol is effective in controlling diabetes mellitus type 2 and also very effective for reducing severity of symptoms like frequent urination, disturbance in sleep, lethargy, numbness

and muscle pain. Diabenol play an important role to enhance the quality of life among diabetic patients. Patient should be encouraged to take homeopathic drugs as an alternative and complementary medicine especially for chronic conditions like diabetes.

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